

QUANTUM NEURAL NETWORK BENCHMARKING: TIME SERIES PREDICTIONS WITH FINANCE FORECASTING AS A USE CASE

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The main goal of this project is to replicate the findings of a 2022 paper by Barclays that utilizes Parametrized Quantum Circuits (PQCs) to forecast financial time series (Emmanoulopoulos & Dimoska, 2022). By faithfully reproducing the work of Dimitrios Emmanoulopoulos and Sofija Dimoska, the project aims to establish a benchmark for PQCs in time series forecasting. This benchmark serves as a foundation for exploring variations in datasets, circuit architectures, and hyperparameters.

To achieve this, the project closely follows the methodology outlined by Emmanoulopoulos and Dimoska to attain similar outcomes using the same dataset, model architecture, and evaluation metrics. Additionally, an alternative circuit architecture is implemented on the same dataset and trained with identical hyperparameters. The resulting outcomes will be compared to the original architecture.

The code is designed with reusability and maintainability in mind, adopting an approach enabling traceability of the experiments with availability on GitHub (<https://github.com/CERN-IT-INNOVATION>). This approach facilitates the expansion of the benchmark to explore various applications of PQCs. Functions and circuits are organized into scripts and libraries, thoroughly documented, and centralized for ease of parameter modification. A Notebook demo is provided for illustrative purposes. The code is optimized for GPU utilization using the JAX machine learning framework from Google.

This report offers a comprehensive overview, summarizing the findings, analysis, and insights derived from the project's endeavors.

ABSTRACT

Machine learning has enabled computers to learn from data and improve their performance on tasks, revolutionizing various industries by automating processes, uncovering insights, and enhancing decision-making. NISQ (Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum) refers to the current stage of quantum computing, characterized by quantum devices with a moderate number of qubits and significant noise. In the NISQ era, parametrized quantum circuits (PQC) are employed in machine learning as flexible quantum algorithms that can be executed on current noisy quantum devices. By introducing tunable parameters, these circuits can adapt to the limitations of NISQ devices, enabling quantum-enhanced solutions to classification and generative tasks while paving the way for practical applications of quantum machine learning.

Time series arise from the abundance of sequential data in various fields, and time series analysis uncovers patterns, trends, and dependencies within the temporal data, enabling informed decision-making and predictions for a wide range of applications. In this project, we aim to replicate the findings of a paper that utilized parametrized quantum circuits (PQCs) to forecast time series data in the context of finance. By faithfully reproducing the original experiments, we seek to establish a benchmark of PQCs for time series predictions. Building upon these results, we further investigate the impact of hyperparameters and explore several circuit architectures to optimize the performance of PQCs in time series forecasting.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION.....	5
1.1	Quantum Computing.....	5
1.1.1	Noisy Intermediate Scale Quantum Devices.....	5
1.1.2	Parametrized Quantum Circuits.....	5
1.2	Machine Learning.....	5
1.2.1	Neural Networks.....	6
1.2.2	Quantum Neural Networks.....	6
1.3	Time Series Predictions.....	6
2	Paper Overview.....	6
3	Replication of Results.....	7
3.1	Data Preprocessing.....	7
3.2	Circuit Architecture.....	9
3.3	Training.....	10
4	Results.....	11
4.1	Hyperparameter exploration.....	13
5	Discussion and Conclusion.....	13
6	Acknowledgments.....	14

1 INTRODUCTION

This project contributes to the ongoing dialogue on the viability of quantum machine learning for practical applications. Results are replicated and extended from a paper conducting a comparative analysis between Quantum Neural Networks (QNNs) and Bi-directional Long Short-Term Memory models (BiLSTMs) for forecasting financial data. This report begins with an introduction of parametrized quantum circuits in the context of the NISQ era of quantum computing and introduces PQC's application as QNNs for time series predictions. Following this introduction, key findings of the original paper are presented, followed by a description of replication efforts to validate these findings. Building upon this foundation, the work is extended by exploring an alternative circuit architecture.

1.1 Quantum Computing

Quantum computing shows promise in transforming computing by harnessing properties of quantum mechanics. Unlike classical computers that use bits to represent 0s and 1s, quantum computers use quantum bits or qubits, which can exist in multiple states simultaneously, enabling quantum algorithms to outperform classical algorithms in terms of time complexity. The potential to solve problems intractable on classical computers has sparked interest and research across scientific disciplines.

1.1.1 Noisy Intermediate Scale Quantum Devices

The Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) era describes the current phase in the development of quantum computing. It is characterized by the availability of quantum devices with a small number of qubits, shallow circuit depth, and significant noise. While NISQ devices may not yet achieve fault-tolerant quantum computation, they provide a unique opportunity to explore quantum algorithms, conduct groundbreaking experiments, and address real-world problems that can benefit from quantum processing.

1.1.2 Parametrized Quantum Circuits

Parametrized Quantum Circuits (PQCs) play a pivotal role in the Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) era, offering a versatile framework for harnessing the potential of quantum devices with limited qubits and high levels of noise. PQCs, equipped with tunable parameters, provide a means to adapt quantum algorithms to the inherent imperfections of NISQ devices, making them resilient to noise and enhancing their performance on specific tasks. PQCs thus offer a current pathway to explore potential quantum advantages and uncover insights in real-world applications.

1.2 Machine Learning

Machine learning has emerged as a cornerstone of modern technological advancements across diverse domains. By leveraging algorithms and models, machine learning enables systems to learn patterns, make predictions, and uncover insights from data. Applications of machine learning range from natural language processing and computer vision to healthcare and finance.

1.2.1 Neural Networks

Neural networks are machine learning models inspired by the human brain's interconnected neurons, designed to learn, and extract patterns from data. There are several proofs of neural networks as universal approximators, meaning they can approximate any continuous function. For example, there exist proofs that convolutional neural networks, recurrent neural networks, and graph neural networks are universal approximators (Anton Maximilian Schäfer & Zimmermann, 2006; Brüel Gabriëlsson, Rickard, 2020; Zhou, 2020). One notable architecture within neural networks is the Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM), which excels in processing sequential data. BiLSTMs leverage both forward and backward information flow through time, enabling them to capture dependencies and nuances in sequential data. BiLSTMs are particularly effective for sequential tasks like natural language processing, where contextual understanding is crucial.

1.2.2 Quantum Neural Networks

Quantum Neural Networks (QNNs) are at the intersection between parametrized quantum circuits and classical neural networks. At the core of QNNs lie PQCs, which serve as the quantum counterparts of the classical neurons in traditional neural networks. PQCs can serve as quantum layers, processing input data using quantum gates. A classical optimizer iteratively adjusts the parametrized gates to minimize a predefined loss function. Thus, QNNs are a hybrid quantum-classical process for learning patterns and making predictions from data.

1.3 Time Series Predictions

Time series data, representing observations recorded over time, are present in many domains including finance and economics. They capture dynamic behaviors, trends, and cyclic patterns that can be used for modeling underlying processes, detecting anomalies, forecasting, and decision making. The accuracy and efficiency of time series analyses are indispensable for understanding temporal relationships and guiding relevant actions. In this report, the potential of PQCs for time series predictions is investigated, using forecasting in finance as a use case.

2 Paper Overview

Classical neural networks, including Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Bidirectional LSTM models, have shown remarkable performance in time series forecasting. LSTMs effectively capture long-range dependencies, while Bi-LSTMs enhance this by considering both past and future context. These models excel at capturing intricate patterns and seasonality, making them suitable for various domains. Time series analysis in the financial sector involves studying chronological sequences of data points to gain knowledge in financial market movements, stock prices, economic indicators, and more. Neural networks' ability to capture complex temporal dependencies has led to successful applications in forecasting stock prices, risk assessment, portfolio optimization, and anomaly detection, contributing to improved decision-making and insights within the financial industry.

Quantum Machine Learning in Finance: Time Series Forecasting by Dimitrios Emmanoulopoulos and Sofija Dimoska is a publication from Barclays comparing the predictive power of Bi-LSTMs to parametrized quantum circuits. Namely, the team investigates the models' ability to forecast the daily percent of change in closing price of Apple stock. The team initially simplified the percent-of-

change signal and added long term trends and noise to increase complexity. In this way, the performance of the models as a function of data complexity was assessed. Finally, the models' performance on the full, unaltered signal was tested. Several metrics were used to compare the PQC performance to the Bi-LSTM: mean squared error, square error standard deviation, mean ratio, and the standard deviation of the ratio. It was found that, in general, the PQC performed similarly to the Bi-LSTM. However, the Bi-LSTM uses 1,830 times more parameters than the PQC. Further, because of large parameter count, the Bi-LSTM tends to overfit noisy data. Emmanoulopoulos and Dimoska concluded that in some circumstances (namely, noisy data and quadratic trends) PQCs can perform better than Bi-LSTMs.

3 Replication of Results

The primary focus of this project was to replicate the procedure conducted by Emmanoulopoulos and Dimoska. In this section, a comprehensive overview details efforts to reproduce this procedure. The process of data preprocessing, the setup of quantum circuit architectures, and the training of models is described, ensuring transparency and reproducibility in this project.

3.1 Data Preprocessing

Following the methodology given by Emmanoulopoulos and Dimoska, AAPL closing prices were obtained from Yahoo finance and were processed to yield the percent of change.

$$\text{percent of change} = \frac{x_{n+1} - x_n}{x_n}$$

To produce a simplified signal, the power spectral density (which gives the component frequencies and associated amplitudes of a signal) was calculated.

$$P(v_k) = \left| \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} x_i e^{\frac{2\pi i j k}{N}} \right|^2$$

Here, x is percent-of-change, N is the number of samples in the data, and k is an integer between 0 and $N/2$. Emmanoulopoulos and Dimoska chose a threshold of $P = 50$ (unitless because the percent-of-change is unitless) to determine the minimum amplitude-squared required to use a component frequency in the simplified signal (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Periodogram with a threshold of amplitude-squared = 50[2]

The resultant component frequencies and their associated amplitudes were used as coefficients in a Fourier sum to construct a simplified signal (Figure 2).

$$signal = \sum_{i=1}^r A_i \sin(v_i x)$$

Figure 2: Signal constructed from the full Apple dataset with a threshold of $P=50$ and no noise or long-term trend added.

A noise signal and long-term trend were also constructed to be added to the simplified signal. The noise was generated as a uniform distribution from 0 to 1, scaled by a noise coefficient and the absolute difference between the maximum and minimum values of the clean signal:

```
import numpy as np
```

```
c_n = [0, 0.2, 0.5, 0.8, 1] # 5 possible noise coefficients
noise_scale = np.abs(np.max(signal) - np.min(signal))
np.random.seed(0)
noise = np.random.uniform(0, 1, N) * noise_scale * (c_n[c_noise])
```

Listing 1: Noise signal construction

The trend was either flat (no trend), linear, or quadratic. Gradients provided by the paper were used to reconstruct the trends:

```
trend = np.array(
    [ np.zeros(N),
      5e-2 * np.linspace(0, N, N),
      2 * 5e-5 * np.square(np.linspace(0, N, N)), ] )
trend = trend.reshape(3, N, 1)
```

Listing 2: Trend construction

3.2 Circuit Architecture

Emmanoulopoulos and Dimoska presented a PQC with a circuit architecture made of Ising gates: XX, YY, and ZZ Ising gates were used to entangle each qubit to the measurement qubit. Each set of entanglements with these gates comprised a layer. 2 layers were used.

This architecture was used to replicate the results of Emmanoulopoulos and Dimoska, and another architecture called matrix product state (MPS) was used to compare performance with another architecture. MPS uses a different strategy for entanglement: each adjacent qubit is entangled with a set of Pauli rotation gates defined in a “block” and a controlled-not gate.

Figure 3: PQC with Ising architecture using 1 layer of entanglement. The Ising gates are composed of parametrized gates which are tuned during training.

Figure 4: Parametrized quantum gate with MPS architecture. The specific choice of gates for entangling adjacent qubits is defined in the orange “block”.

Using the simplified signal with no noise or trend added as the simplest dataset, the two circuits were trained.

3.3 Training

To partition the complete dataset of size N into the training and testing sets, a filter was advanced across the dataset with a stride of 1 to yield $(N - n) + 1$ groups. The number of elements in each group is defined as the number of qubits ‘ n ’ in the PQC.

Figure 4: Data regrouping method for increasing training size. Each of the four rows is a “group”.

These groups of size n were shuffled, 2/3 were used to create a training set and 1/3 comprised the testing set. The first $n - 1$ values in each n -sized group constituted the input for the model, while the last value was the target.

To accelerate the training process, JAX was used. JAX is an open-source library that extends NumPy to enable GPU-accelerated computation and automatic differentiation. Jax provided a ~6,000% speedup on training the Ising model, reducing training time from 40 days to just 14 hours. Two key modifications were made to implement Jax. First, the cost function was vectorized, allowing multiple circuit computations to be performed simultaneously. This was achieved by redefining the circuit as a function using the “vmap” transformation from Jax. This function differed from the circuit in accepting data of one more dimension: (circuit input size \times batch size) as opposed to just (circuit input size). Differentiating the resulting function using Jax.grad enabled training with gradient descend. Loss was calculated as mean squared error between the circuit predictions and target values.

Ten training steps were used per epoch and the model was trained for 300 epochs with a learning rate of 0.1. This training procedure was used both for the Ising and MPS PQCs.

4 Results

This section presents findings and a comparison with the original results from Barclays. A discussion of observed discrepancies is also presented.

The selected metric for comparison between the outcomes presented by Emmanoulopoulos and Dimoska and the results achieved through the replication of their approach was the mean squared error (MSE). The replicated Ising PQC and MPS PQC demonstrated MSE values of 0.0055 and 0.00122, respectively, in contrast to the MSE of 0.00157 obtained from the Barclays Ising PQC (Figure 8).

Figure 5: Loss curve obtained from training the PQC with Ising architecture (left) and the PQC with MPS architecture (right) for 300 epochs.

Figure 6: Predictions made by the trained model with Ising (left) and MPS (right) architecture.

Each of the three PQCs yielded notably higher mean squared error (MSE) values compared to the score of $2e - 5$ accomplished by the Barclays BiLSTM model. Additionally, all three models were surpassed in performance by the forward model. The forward model serves as a straightforward benchmark for evaluating the effectiveness of machine learning models, utilizing the most recent data as the prediction basis. For instance, if the initial five natural numbers are given as inputs, the

forward model predicts the last number in the sequence, the fifth natural number, as the next value.

The lower MSE of the forward compared to the PQCs suggests low complexity in the data because forwards perform well for data that is nearly constant. Indeed, the high sampling frequency of the data results in a small change in consecutive datapoints (Figure 7). PQCs are described by Fourier sums and therefore would likely outperform the forward for regressions of data with trigonometric patterns and lower sampling frequency.

Figure 7: The first 3 inputs and targets from the shuffled training set. Each input consists of 14 values with the first 13 being the inputs for the PQC and the last being the target value.

Figure 8: Comparison of MSE obtained from all 5 models: Barclays’s Ising and BiLSTM, My Ising and MPS, and the forward.

In future work, the forwards should be evaluated on all datasets used in the work of Emmanoulopoulos and Dimoska to provide additional context for the performance of the PQCs and the BiLSTM.

4.1 Hyperparameter exploration

In future work we suggest an exploration of the impact of different hyperparameters. This may include varying learning rates, batch sizes, and sampling techniques to assess the influence of these hyperparameters on accuracy and convergence speed.

Furthermore, we propose exploring alternative circuit architectures, such as tree tensor networks, inspired by the enhanced performance observed in the circuit using a tensor network structure—the MPS PQC. Additionally, different numbers of layers and block configurations should be explored to investigate the effect of changing entanglement patterns. Investigating this with datasets from various domains and of varying complexities may reveal design choices that would further enhance PQC performance for specific use cases. Namely, datasets with a lower sampling frequency may have increased complexity, likely illuminating use cases in which PQCs outperform the forward and possibly classical neural networks.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

This project aimed to replicate the results of the Ising PQC presented by Emmanoulopoulos and Dimoska in their paper *Quantum Machine Learning in Finance: Time Series Forecasting*. Specifically, the results were obtained for the case of a simplified signal constructed with components above a threshold of 50 and with no added noise or long-term trend. A PQC using the same architecture as presented by Emmanoulopoulos and Dimoska resulted in a higher MSE than what was achieved in the original paper. Possible reasons for this include incomplete training due to a larger-than-optimal learning rate, or an error in replication of the PQC or scaling methods. Different weight initialization should also be explored in future work to assess the impact on final MSE.

A PQC using an MPS architecture was tested on the same dataset and yielded an MSE ~22% lower than what was achieved in the original paper. Whether this difference holds any statistical significance should be investigated further. The forward was also calculated on the dataset as a benchmark against which to compare other results. It was found that the forward, the most trivial algorithm, outperformed all three PQCs but was outperformed by the BiLSTM. It was inferred that the high sampling frequency of the data was the reason for the strong performance of the forward relative to all PQCs. Thus, to investigate a use case where PQCs may have an advantage over more conventional methods, datasets with lower sampling frequencies (more complexity in small intervals) should be tested.

In addition to the short-term objective of manually exploring new circuit architectures, training hyperparameters, and datasets, a step further would be to implement an automatic hyperparameter optimization scheme. Several frameworks exist for this task including RayTune, an open-source Python library for efficient hyperparameter tuning and experimentation.

Further, it is suggested to extend the open-source code, which is available on GitHub, for implementation on quantum hardware. This may be achieved, for example, using the Pennylane-Qiskit plugin which offers access to various quantum simulators and quantum hardware backends. Circuit compilation is performed automatically, allowing implementation of many circuit architectures with minimal changes to code.

Implementation on hardware enables a more complete assessment of circuit performance as the constraints of presently accessible hardware directly impact results. Investigations in this area would identify resilient circuit architectures. For example, it is expected that circuit architectures with low depth and few swap gates would achieve similar performance on hardware compared to simulators: these architectures are exposed to less noise than those using extensive entanglement patterns.

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